

PI index of tetrathiafulvalene dendrimers[†]

Ali Reza Ashrafi* and Hossein Shabani

Department of Mathematics, Statistics and Computer Science, Faculty of Science, University of Kashan,
Kashan 87317-51167, I. R. Iran

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Abstract : The Padmakar-Ivan (PI) index of a graph G is defined as $PI(G) = \sum_{e=uv} [m_u(e) + m_v(e)]$, where $m_u(e)$ is the number of edges of G lying closer to u than to v , $m_v(e)$ is defined analogously and summation goes over all edges of G . In this paper, the PI index of tetrathiafulvalene (TTF) dendrimer is computed, whereby TTF units were employed as branching centers.

Keywords : Dendrimer, PI index.

Introduction

A molecular graph is a simple graph such that its vertices correspond to the atoms and the edges to the bonds. Note that hydrogen atoms are often omitted¹⁻³. By IUPAC terminology, a topological index is a numerical value associated with a chemical constitution purporting for correlation of chemical structure with various physical properties, chemical reactivity or biological activity. This concept was first proposed by Hosoya⁴ for characterizing the topological nature of a graph.

Dendrimers are generally described as a macromolecule, which is built from a starting atom, such as nitrogen, to which carbon and other elements are added by a repeating series of chemical reactions that produce a spherical branching structure. In a divergent synthesis of a dendrimer, one starts from the core (a multi connected atom or group of atoms) and grows out to the periphery. In each repeated step, a number of monomers are added to the actual structure, in a radial manner, in resulting quasi concentric shells, called generations. In a convergent synthesis, the periphery is first built up and next the branches (called dendrons) are connected to the core. The stepwise growth of a dendrimer follows a mathematical progression and its size is in the nanometer scale⁵⁻⁷.

We now recall some algebraic definitions that will be used in the paper. Let G be a simple molecular graph without directed and multiple edges and without loops,

the vertex and edge-sets of which are represented by $V(G)$ and $E(G)$, respectively. e is an edge of G , connecting the vertices u and v then we write $e = uv$. If x and y are arbitrary vertices of a connected graph G then $d(x,y)$ denotes the length of a shortest path connecting them. The oldest distance-based topological index is the Wiener index which introduced by Harold Wiener⁸. It is defined as the sum of all distances between pair of vertices in G . John Platt was the only person who immediately realized the importance of the Wiener's pioneering work and wrote papers analyzing and interpreting the physical meaning of the Wiener index. Many topological indices have been defined and several of them have found applications as means to model physical, chemical, pharmaceutical and other properties of molecules^{9,10}.

Suppose G is a graph. The PI index is the first topological index considered the distance between edges as those of vertices. To explain, we assume that G is a graph, $x \in V(G)$ and $e = uv$ is an edge of G . Define $D(x,e) = \text{Min}\{d(x,u), d(x,v)\}$. An edge f is said to be equidistant from both ends of the edge $e = uv$ if $D(u,f) = d(v,f)$. Set $M_u(e) = \{f | D(u,f) < D(v,f)\}$, $M_v(e) = \{f | D(u,f) > D(v,f)\}$, $m_u(e) = |M_u(e)|$ and $m_v(e) = |M_v(e)|$. Following Khadikar¹¹ we define the PI index of a molecular graph G to be the sum of $m_u(e) + m_v(e)$ over all edges of G . Notice that edges equidistant from both ends of the edge uv are not counted. Khadikar and his team¹²⁻³² investigated the behavior of some physico-chemical quanti-

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

Fig. 1. TTF dendrimer (a) DNS [1]; (b) DNS [2].

ties under this topological index. After the pioneering work of Padmakar Khadikar, some researchers considered the mathematical properties and chemical meaning of this topological index into account. One of the present author (ARA)³³⁻⁵³, computed the PI index of some classes of fullerenes, nanotubes, nanocones, dendrimers and nanostars. The motivation of this study is taken from some leading works of a Romanian chemist M. V. Diudea and his team⁵⁴⁻⁶⁴. We encourage the reader to consult papers⁶⁵⁻⁷⁵ for some computational techniques which is important for working by molecular graphs of nanostructures and papers⁷⁶⁻⁹⁹ for mathematical properties of PI index.

In this paper, the PI index of a class of dendrimers named tetrathiafulvalene (TTF), Fig. 1, is computed, whereby TTF units were employed as branching centers⁷.

Main Results and discussion

In this section, the PI index of the molecular graph $T = DNS[k]$, $k \geq 1$, were computed. This is a graph with exactly $128 \times 2^k - 78$ vertices. To do this, we assume that $E = E(T)$ is the set of all edges and $M(e) = |E| - (m_u(e) + m_v(e))$. Then $PI(T) = |E|^2 - \sum_{e \in E} M(e)$. Since $|E(T)| = 140 \times 2^k - 85$, $PI(T) = [140 \times 2^k - 85]^2 - \sum_{e \in E} M(e)$. Therefore, for computing the PI index of T , it is enough to calculate $M(e)$, for every $e \in E$.

To compute the PI index of T , we first consider a partition of $E(T)$ into two subsets A and B such that A

contains the edges of the core, Fig. 2, and B is the set of all remaining edges of T , Fig. 3. Thus $PI = \sum_{e \in A} \{m_u(v)\}$

Fig. 2. A labeling of some edges for the core of T

Fig. 3. A labeling of some edges for one of the branches of T .

$$+ m_v(f)] + \sum_{e \in B} [m_u(e) + m_v(e)].$$

By the symmetry of core, it is enough to compute $M(f_i)$, where $1 \leq i \leq 12$. In Table 1, $m_u(f_i)$, $m_v(f_i)$ and L_i , the number of similar edges as f_i , are given.

Table 1. The values of $m_u(f_i)$, $m_v(f_i)$ and L_i , for the edges of core

	$m_u(f_i)$	$m_v(f_i)$	L_i	$m_u(f_i) + m_v(f_i)$
f_1	$64 \times 2^k - 39$	$64 \times 2^k - 39$	1	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
f_2	$64 \times 2^k - 37$	$12 + 32(2^k - 1)$	4	$105 \times 2^k - 64$
f_3	$64 \times 2^k - 37$	$64 \times 2^k - 42$	4	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
f_4	$32 \times 2^k - 20$	$12 + 32(2^k - 1)$	2	$70 \times 2^k - 44$
f_5	$96 \times 2^k - 56$	$10 + 32(2^k - 1)$	4	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
f_6	$96 \times 2^k - 55$	$9 + 32(2^k - 1)$	4	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
f_7	$96 \times 2^k - 54$	$8 + 32(2^k - 1)$	4	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
f_8	$96 \times 2^k - 53$	$5 + 32(2^k - 1)$	8	$140 \times 2^k - 87$
f_9	$96 \times 2^k - 51$	$5 + 32(2^k - 1)$	8	$140 \times 2^k - 87$
f_{10}	$96 \times 2^k - 51$	$5 + 32(2^k - 1)$	8	$140 \times 2^k - 87$
f_{11}	$96 \times 2^k - 48$	$2 + 32(2^k - 1)$	4	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
f_{12}	$96 \times 2^k - 47$	$1 + 32(2^k - 1)$	4	$140 \times 2^k - 86$

By Table 1, $\sum_{f \in A} [m_u(f) + m_v(f)] = 1 \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 4 \times (105 \times 2^k - 64) + 4 \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 2 \times (70 \times 2^k - 44) + 4 \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 4 \times (140 \times$

$$2^k - 86) + 4 \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 8 \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 8 \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 8 \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 4 \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 4 \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) = 7420 \times 2^k - 4558.$$

In Table 2, $m_u(f_i)$, $m_v(f_i)$ and L_i , the number of similar edges as f_i , for a representative set of edges in B are given.

By Table 2, $\sum_{e \in B} [m_u(e) + m_v(e)] = 4(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 4 \sum_{1 \leq i \leq k} (2^{i-1}) [140 \times 2^k - 70 \times 2^k \times 2^{-i} - 44] + 4(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 4(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 4(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 4(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 87) + 4 \sum_{1 \leq i \leq k} (2^{i-1}) [70 \times 2^k \times 2^{-i} - 37] + 4(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 8 \sum_{1 \leq i \leq k} (2^{i-1}) [140 \times 2^k - 35 \times 2^k \times 2^{-i} - 62] + 8(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 4 \sum_{1 \leq i \leq k} (2^{i-1}) [26 + 70(2^{k-i} - 1)] + 8(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 8(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 8(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 87) + 16(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 87) + 16(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 87) + 8(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) + 8(2^k - 1) \times (140 \times 2^k - 86) = 18480 \times 2^k - 29848 \times 2^k + 11368.$

Table 2. The values of $m_u(f_i)$, $m_v(f_i)$ and L_i , for the edges of a branch of T

	$m_u(f_i)$	$m_v(f_i)$	L_i	$m_u(f_i) + m_v(f_i)$
e_1	$70 \times 2^k - 43$	$70 \times 2^k - 43$	$4(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
e_2	$58 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1)$	3	$4(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 70 \times 2^k \times 2^{-i} - 44$
e_3	$140 \times 2^k - 86$	0	$4(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
e_4	$59 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1)$	$30 + 70(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$4(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
e_5	$59 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1)$	$30 + 70(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$4(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
e_6	$58 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1)$	$30 + 70(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$4(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 87$
e_7	3	$30 + 70(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$4(2^{i-1})$	$70 \times 2^k \times 2^{-i} - 37$
e_8	$62 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1)$	$27 + 70(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$4(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
e_9	$65 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1)$	$13 + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$8(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 35 \times 2^k \times 2^{-i} - 62$
e_{10}	$65 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1)$	$24 + 70(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$8(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
e_{11}	$13 + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$13 + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$4(2^{i-1})$	$26 + 70(2^{k-i} - 1)$
e_{12}	$79 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1) + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$10 + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$8(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
e_{13}	$80 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1) + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$9 + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$8(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
e_{14}	$81 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1) + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$8 + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$8(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
e_{15}	$84 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1) + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$4 + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$16(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 87$
e_{16}	$84 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1) + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$4 + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$16(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 87$
e_{17}	$84 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1) + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$4 + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$16(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 87$
e_{18}	$88 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1) + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$1 + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$8(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 86$
e_{19}	$89 + 140(2^k - 1) - 35(2^{k-i+1} - 1) + 35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$35(2^{k-i} - 1)$	$8(2^{i-1})$	$140 \times 2^k - 86$

From these calculations we have :

Theorem : The PI index of $T = DNS[k]$ is as follows :

$$PI(DNS[k]) = 18480 \times 4^k - 22428 \times 2^k + 6810$$

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